

The Great Pyramid and π @ 3.14159

How many digits are enough?

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Abstract

It is well known that the Great Pyramid's dimensions approximate π , as twice the base over the height is $\frac{22}{7}$. The dimensions also provide approximations for the golden ratio φ , Euler's number e , and the speed of light c [1]. In this document I show how the outer dimensions, plus the Kings chamber floor, lead directly to a value of 3.14159. This is precise enough to limit the error on the circumference of a 10 km diameter circle, which is about 31.4 km, to a mere 2.65 cm [2].

Keywords: Pyramids of Giza, History of Mathematics, π

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1 Introduction

Approximations for π are found all over Giza, and especially in the Great Pyramid. For a discussion about this, please refer to my paper *Ramanujan and the Pyramid of Venus at Giza* [1].

I was recently led to a very good approximations for π , at 3.14159, embedded in the Great Pyramid's dimensions.

This value, and even the very concept of π , challenges the accepted time-line, because the existing New Kingdom mathematical papyri make it clear that the dynastic Egyptians did not know of π .

2 3.14159 from areas

The method is quite simple, and the result follows from adding the area of one side to the area of the King's Chamber floor, illustrated by the green lines in Figure 1.

Figure 1: One side plus the King's Chamber floor

The King's Chamber is arguably the most important room in the pyramid that we have documented. It refers to π several times, in the dimensions (*Observations on the King's Chamber Dimensions* [3]), and in the patterns of the wall blocks (*The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game* [4], *$\sqrt{10\pi}$ on Khufu's King's Chamber Walls* [5]).

The Great Pyramid is accepted to have had a design base of 440 royal cubits (€) square, and a height of 280 €.

To calculate the area of a side, we first need the slant height, which we get via Pythagoras:

Slant height = square root of (half base squared plus height squared) = $\sqrt{220^2 + 280^2} = 356.0898763$. The extra decimals here are necessary.

Then the area of a side, which is a triangle, is

Side area = half (base \times slant height) = $\frac{1}{2}(440 \times 356.0898763) = 78339.77278$ €².

The King's Chamber is $10 \times 20 = 200$ €². We add these two results together, getting 78539.77278 €².

At this point we can go in two different directions, leading to different expressions of the required digits.

2.1 Approach 1

Divide by 25000 to get π correct to five decimals,

$$\frac{78539.77278}{25000} = 3.141590911, \text{ or } 3.14159 \text{ to five decimals.}$$

2.2 Approach 2

Alternatively, we can multiply by 4 to get $100,000 \times 3.14159$, rounded.

$$78539.77278 \times 4 = 314,159.0911, \text{ or } 100,000 \text{ times } 3.14159 \text{ rounded.}$$

2.3 Approach 3

There is a third approach. In *The Beautiful System* [6] I proposed a hypothetical Royal Inch, for which there is no known evidence, but which has interesting mathematical properties. Its length is 2.618cm, which is 0.78mm longer than the current imperial inch. The properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The proposed Royal Inch

Item	Length cm	Comment
Royal inch	2.618	φ^2 cm
Half cubit	26.18	10 inches, $10 \varphi^2$ cm
Royal foot	31.416	12 inches, 10π cm
Cubit	52.36	20 inches, $1\frac{2}{3}$ feet

To do the calculation in Royal Inches instead of \mathcal{G} , we multiply each \mathcal{G} value by 20, and get

$$\text{Side area} = \text{half}(\text{base} \times \text{height}) = \frac{1}{2}(440 \times 20 \times 356.0898763 \times 20) = 31335909.11$$

The King's Chamber is $(10 \times 20) \times (20 \times 20) = 80000$ square inches.

We add there two results together: $31335909.11 + 80000 = 31415909.11$.

Dividing by 10 million and rounding to 5 places gives us 3.14159 again.

3 Discussion

Egyptologists usually dismiss the Great Pyramid's " $\frac{22}{7}$ " π approximation as an accidental by-product of the chosen slope angle. Critics also like to point out that " $\frac{22}{7}$ is not π ", while glossing over the fact that it is not possible to get π as the ratio of two integers anyway. All decimal versions of π are approximations with varying degrees of accuracy. Even NASA only uses 15 decimals (*How Many Decimals of Pi Do We Really Need?* [7]).

If we went to Mars and found the Khufu and Khafre pyramids there, next to each other, we would recognise them for what they are: pyramids based on the Kepler triangle and the classic 3-4-5 Pythagorean triangle. These two right-angled triangles are unique: Kepler has the sides in geometric progression ($1 : \sqrt{\varphi} : \varphi$), where each side is the next smaller multiplied by $\sqrt{\varphi}$, while the Pythagorean uses arithmetic progression. Space scientists would have no trouble understanding the implications of these pyramids. They would not assign their construction next to each other, and design paradigms, as "random luck."

Giza is a set of "layered revelations." Simple things, like Khafre's 3-4-5 design, are easy to see. Khufu's design requires slightly more advanced mathematics. The π approximation ($\frac{22}{7}$) is not very precise, but it is still widely used around the world, and was put there to be discovered ... and as a hint to look deeper. When we look deeper, we find approximations for π all over. When we go inside the Great Pyramid, to the king's chamber, then the approximations become much more precise, if you read the walls correctly. These topics are discussed multiple times in my various other papers listed in the bibliography.

This calculation only works with the Great Pyramid's dimensions of 440×280 , and is thus not a co-incidental by-product of the chosen slope angle.

If we run the calculation backwards, starting with 314159 and a base of 440 \mathcal{G} , to determine the ideal height, it works out at 279.9998683 \mathcal{G} . So 280 \mathcal{G} is the practical height to use.

If we set π to 3.14159 and use engineering equality instead of mathematical equality, then we can write the equations (which are equivalent versions of the same equality) as

$$\frac{100,000\pi}{4} = \text{area of side} + \text{king's chamber floor}$$

$$\frac{\text{area of side} + \text{king's chamber floor}}{25,000} = \pi$$

The Great Pyramid is the only pyramid that has this version of π embedded in its dimensions.

The dynastic Egyptians used fractional notation, not our positional base ten notation. This result suggests that the builders used the same notation as us, and could thus not have been the 4th dynasty as we know it.

Critics may claim that this is just another co-incidence. It is difficult to counter that claim, we would need to work out the exact odds of this working and then decide how likely that is.

If we keep the king's chamber dimensions fixed, and vary the base, we can calculate the required ideal height for different base sizes. We then need to round that to the nearest \mathcal{G} , and see how accurate the result is. This is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of effect of different sizes on π value

Base	Ideal height	Actual height	" π "	int(π)	Delta
426	299.8369	300	314272.3251	314272	113
427	298.4226	298	313865.5559	313866	293
428	297.0082	297	314153.2953	314153	6
429	295.5936	296	314441.2516	314441	282
430	294.1788	294	314034.8569	314035	124
431	292.7637	293	314323.0988	314323	164
432	291.3481	291	313917.4622	313917	242
433	289.9320	290	314206.1657	314206	47
434	288.5154	289	314495.2480	314495	336
435	287.0982	287	314090.9139	314091	68
436	285.6802	286	314380.7055	314381	222
437	284.2615	284	313977.8115	313978	181
438	282.8419	283	314268.4941	314268	109
439	281.4214	281	313867.3336	313867	292
440	279.9999	280	314159.0911	314159	0
441	278.5772	279	314451.4649	314451	292
442	277.1534	277	314052.9807	314053	106
443	275.7283	276	314346.6876	314347	188
444	274.3019	274	313950.6536	313951	208
445	272.8741	273	314245.8829	314246	87
446	271.4447	271	313852.6072	313853	306
447	270.0137	270	314149.5506	314150	9
448	268.5811	269	314447.3564	314447	288
449	267.1466	267	314058.1970	314058	101
450	265.7104	266	314357.9851	314358	199
451	264.2721	264	313972.3346	313972	187
452	262.8318	263	314274.3018	314274	115
453	261.3894	261	313892.4829	313892	267
454	259.9447	260	314196.8281	314197	38

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